

SURFACE LAYER OF GRAPHENE STRUCTURES

Yurov V.,

Candidate of phys.-mat. sciences, associate professor
TSK Vostok LLP, Karaganda, Kazakhstan

Zhangozin K.,

Candidate of Physics and Mathematics Sciences, Associate Professor,
TSK Vostok LLP, Astana, Kazakhstan

Kargin D.

Candidate of Physics and Mathematics Sciences, Associate Professor,
NAO "L.N. Gumilyov Eurasian National University",
Astana, Kazakhstan**Abstract**

Graphene structures arise by introducing functional groups, doping and changing the morphology of the graphene layer. The aim of the article is to determine the surface layer of graphene structures and compare them with graphite and graphene. Samples for study: graphite, graphene, graphite oxide, graphene oxide, fluorographite, fluorographene and graphane. Research method: empirical model for determining the thickness of the surface layer; determination of the specific adhesion energy; calculation of the deformation energy of the surface layer. The deformation energy under external influence is spent on heat, acoustic emission, field emission and luminescence. The article shows that all graphene structures contain three graphene monolayers, each of which differs from each other and from the volume of the crystal, thereby giving wide scope for their practical use. Luminescence is not observed in graphene, fluorographene and graphane.

Keywords: graphite, graphene, graphite oxide, graphene oxide, fluorographite, fluorographene, surface layer, luminescence, deformation energy.

Introduction

Graphene structures arise by introducing functional groups, doping and changing the morphology of the graphene layer. This leads to a reconfiguration of the π -conjugated electron cloud due to the partial transformation of sp^2 -hybridized carbon atoms into sp^3 -hybridized ones, as well as the inductive effect from the presence of donor or acceptor functional groups. More details about all this can be found in reviews [1-4].

The aim of the article is to determine the surface layer of graphene structures and compare them with graphite and graphene.

Graphene structures (brief review)

Graphite is a layered 3D structure. Each of these layers consists of regular hexagons of carbon atoms (C) measuring 0.335 nm, between which strong covalent bonds act with an energy of 170 J/mol. Between the layers there is a space of 0.7-1.6 nm, where weak van der Waals forces act with an energy of 16.7 J/mol (Fig. 1a). These graphene layers slide easily in the longitudinal direction and represent a solid lubricant (Fig. 1b) [5].

Figure 1.

Graphite structure (a) and diagram of the layer on metal (the dotted line indicates the easy shear plane) (b) [5].

The first monolayer of graphite – graphene (Fig. 2), has strong covalent σ -bonds C–C in the plane of the graphene sheet in combination with π -electrons outside it, which determines the unique physicochemical properties of graphene, such as a large theoretical specific

surface area ($\sim 2600 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$), high mobility of charge carriers ($\sim 200,000 \text{ cm}^2/\text{V}\cdot\text{s}$), high Young's modulus ($\sim 1000 \text{ GPa}$), thermal conductivity ($\sim 5000 \text{ W/m K}$), optical transparency ($\sim 97.7\%$), mechanical strength, etc. [6, 7].

Figure 2. – Graphene structure (a); corrugated graphene (b) [6, 7].

Graphene oxide (GO) is a berthollide, i.e. a compound of variable composition that changes depending on the method and conditions of production, in connection with which various structural models of GO have historically been presented (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. - Structural models of graphene oxide: a) Hoffman model; b) Ress model; c) Scholz-Boehm model; d) Dekaney model; e) Nakajima-Matsuo model; e) Lerf-Klinovsky model [8]

The chemical composition of graphene oxide and oxygen-containing functional groups can be determined using such spectroscopic methods of analysis as Raman spectroscopy, infrared spectroscopy (IR), solid-state nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR), X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) [8-10].

NMR spectra show that the main lines in the graphene oxide spectrum correspond to: a peak at about 60

ppm to carbon atoms associated with epoxy functional groups; a peak at about 70 ppm corresponds to carbon atoms associated with hydroxyl groups; a peak at about 130 ppm refers to sp^2 -carbon atoms. Three more peaks at 101, 167 and 191 ppm are determined for lactone, carbonyl and ketone groups (Fig. 4).

Figure 4. - NMR spectrum of graphene oxide [11]

The XPS method reveals the nature of carbon and oxygen bonds in their various states: unoxidized carbon atoms (sp^2 -carbon), C-O-C, C=O and COOH. The C1s signal of GO (Fig. 5) consists of five different chemical components that can be converted into sp^2 -carbon atoms (284.5 eV) and carbon atoms associated with hydroxyl (C-OH, 285.86 eV), epoxy (C-O-C, 286.55 eV),

carbonyl (C=O, 287.5 eV) and carboxyl groups (COOH, 289.2 eV).

The Raman spectrum of GO displays a broad G-peak at 1580 cm^{-1} which is characteristic of all sp^2 -hybridized carbon. In addition, the Raman spectrum contains D, Dr and D+G bands at 1330 cm^{-1} , 1620 cm^{-1} and 2915 cm^{-1} , which arise from structural defects (Fig. 6).

Figure 5. - XPS spectrum of graphene oxide [12]

Figure 6. - Raman spectra of graphene oxide: a) depending on the type of reducing agent [13]; b) depending on the reduction temperature [12]

Graphene can participate in a large number of chemical reactions of organic synthesis and aromatic chemistry. Using these reactions, various organic groups containing halogens (Br, Cl, F, I), chalcogens (O, S), pnictogens (N, P, Sb, Bi) or silicon, as well as more complex functional groups such as alkyl and aryl hydrocarbons, can be covalently attached to the edges

or basal plane of graphene [14-17] (Fig. 7). In addition, graphene can also be doped, where carbon atoms in the graphene lattice are replaced by atoms of other elements such as nitrogen, phosphorus, sulfur or boron [18,19].

Figure 7.

Scheme of graphene modification with various organic groups and compounds, in particular oxygen groups (-OH; -COOH), amines (NH), halogens (Cl), thiols (SH), ethers (-O-R), aromatic compounds (-S-Benz; -O-Benz) [1]

Depending on the degree of graphene functionalization (FG), that is, the relative number of carbon atoms in the graphene lattice associated with modifying organic groups or doping atoms, FG are divided into stoichiometric and non-stoichiometric. To date, only two stoichiometric derivatives of graphene have been obtained - graphene covalently modified with fluorine (C-F) and hydrogen (C-H) atoms, called fluorographene and graphane, respectively [20, 21].

Graphite is an allotropic modification of carbon with an atomic mass of 12.0107 g/mol, a density of 2.26 g/cm³ and sp²-hybridization of carbon atoms [22]. If fluorine atoms are attached to the carbon atoms of graphite, then sp²-hybridization changes to sp³-hybridization, but hexagonal symmetry is retained [23]. The structure is shown (Fig. 8 a and b).

Figure 8. Crystal lattice structure: graphite (a); fluorographite (b).

If you split off one layer from graphite, you will get graphene (Fig. 9a), and if you split off one layer from fluorographite, you will get fluorographene [23] (Fig. 9b).

Figure 9. The structure of graphene (a) and fluorographene in the chair conformation (b) [23].

We will consider graphite fluoride in the form of $\text{CF}_{0.96}$ [24], where the following are determined: molecular weight $M = 30.2492 \text{ g/mol}$, density $\rho = 2.33 \text{ g/cm}^3$. The lattice parameters are as follows [25]: $a = b = 0.5034 \text{ nm}$; $c = 1.123 \text{ nm}$. Melting temperatures: for graphite $T_m = 3650 \text{ K}$ [26]; for fluorographite $T_m = 773 \text{ K}$ [27].

No less unique material is graphane, obtained as a result of the addition of hydrogen atoms to carbon atoms of the graphite structure [20, 21]. This material also has a crystalline structure and retains the original crystal lattice, but with a different, significantly smaller lattice pitch than graphene (Fig. 10).

Figure 10. – Graphane crystal structure: C – carbon (green); H – hydrogen (white) [20, 21]

The speed of sound for graphane was $50,334 \text{ m/s}$ [28], which is much higher than the values for graphite ($1,470 \text{ m/s}$), diamond ($12,000\text{--}18,350 \text{ m/s}$), single-walled carbon nanotubes ($31,470 \text{ m/s}$), and graphene ($13,600\text{--}21,300 \text{ m/s}$). Phonon spectra allow us to determine the Debye temperature: $T_D = 6,052 \text{ K}$. For comparison, it should be noted that the T_D value of a related material composed of carbon atoms, diamond, is $2,230 \text{ K}$, and for graphene it is $1,612 \text{ K}$. For most solids, it

lies within the range of $100 \div 400 \text{ K}$. The anomalous value of the Debye temperature for diamond is explained by the high energy of chemical bonds - 7.5 eV . The T_D value of graphane estimated in the work turns out to be high for the same reason.

In [29], the methods of density functional theory in the gradient approximation were used to calculate the structure and electronic properties of polymorphic varieties of graphane. It was found that there may be five

main structural varieties of graphane, in which the carbon atoms are in crystallographically equivalent states. As a result of calculations of the band structure and the density of electronic states, it was found that the width of the forbidden band at the Fermi level for graphane polymorphs varies from 5.50 to 5.65 eV. The sublimation energy of graphane layers with different structures differs insignificantly, changing in the range from 11.3 to 11.5 eV/atom.

In the work [30] as a result of theoretical analysis the possibility of existence of twenty six diamond-like phases was established, of which 8 are graphanes, 8 are tubulanes, 10 are fullerenes. Graphane phases can only be of the graphane-A type, i.e. they can be obtained

Figure 11. - Scheme for obtaining graphane-A2 from L6 graphene layers [30]

The properties of graphane-A2 determined as a result of model calculations: density (ρ): 3.488 g/cm³; packing coefficient (f): 0.340; sublimation energy (E_{sub}): 166.3 kcal/mol; bulk modulus (K): 474 GPa. Structural characteristics of graphane-A2: $a = b = 0.2522$ nm; $c = 0.4152$ nm.

Surface layer of graphene structures

J. Gibbs represented the surface of a solid as a geometric plane with no thickness [31]. However, van der Waals [32] and Guggenheim [33] considered the surface layer as a layer of finite thickness, the size of which was empirically determined in [34]. According to modern concepts, the surface layer is an ultra-thin film in thermodynamic equilibrium with the volume of

a)

only as a result of crosslinking of graphene layers, graphane B phases do not exist. Designations of diamond-like phases according to the developed classification scheme correspond to the names of previously known phases as follows: graphane-A1 – cubic diamond, graphane-A2 – lonsdaleite, graphane-A3 – rectangular or bct C4, graphane-A4 – diamond-like BC8 phase, fullerane-A3 – supercubane. The crystalline structure of graphane-A2 is obtained by cross-linking graphene layers consisting of hexagons in such a way that every three atoms of each hexagon of one layer form three bonds with the atoms of the lower layer, and the remaining three atoms form bonds with the atoms of the upper layer (Fig. 11).

the rest of the crystal [35]. Experimentally, the thickness of this film can be measured in ultra-high vacuum using the sliding X-ray method [36].

We first determined the thickness of the surface layer of graphite and graphene in [37-40] (Fig. 12a), and the dependence of ν on Z in Fig. 1b. The thickness of the surface layer $R(I)$ is given by the formula [37]:

$$R(I) = 0,17 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot \alpha \cdot \nu [m]. \quad (1)$$

In equation (1) you need to know one parameter – the molar volume of the element, which is equal to $\nu = M/\rho$ (M is the molar mass, ρ is its density), $\alpha = 1 \text{ mol m}^{-2}$ is a constant to maintain the dimensionality ($R(I)$ [m]).

b)

Figure 12. - Scheme of a solid: nanolayer → mesolayer → bulk phase (a); corrugated graphene (b)

In [38] it is shown that the surface energy of a bulk metal γ_2 with an accuracy of 3% is equal to:

$$\gamma_2 = 0,7 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot T_m [\text{J/m}^2], \quad (2)$$

where T_m is the melting temperature of the metal (K).

In the $R(I)$ layer, the size effect must be taken into account and the surface energy becomes equal to γ_1 [39]:

$$\gamma_1 = \gamma_2 (1 - R(I) / R(I) + h) \approx 0,5 \gamma_2, \quad (3)$$

To separate the $R(I)$ layer from the rest of the crystal, energy must be expended, which is called the specific energy of adhesion.:

$$W_a = \gamma_1 + \gamma_2 - \gamma_{12} \approx \gamma_1 + \gamma_2. \quad (4)$$

We calculate the internal stresses σ_{is} between phases γ_1 and γ_2 using the formula:

$$\sigma_{is} = \sqrt{W_a \cdot E / R(I)}, \quad (5)$$

where E is Young's modulus of elasticity.

The energy of deformation E_d between phases γ_1 and γ_2 is calculated:

$$E_d = W_a \cdot a^2, \quad (6)$$

where a is the lattice constant.

Using (1), we calculate the parameters of graphene structures.

Table 1.

Surface layer thickness R(I) of graphene structures					
Carbon	M, g/mol	ρ , g/sm	$R(I)_a$, nm	$R(I)_c$, nm	γ_a , mJ/m ²
Graphite	12,0	2,26	0,900 (3)	2,46 (3)	2195
Graphene	12,0	2,26	0,246 (1)	0,14 (1)	2652
Graphite oxide	72,0	2,42	1,870 (3)	5,11 (3)	1931
Graphene oxide	72,0	2,42	0,412 (1)	1,53 (1)	1311
Fluorographite	30,25	2,33	2,03 (3)	6,41 (3)	361
Fluorographene	30,25	2,33	0,551 (1)	1,60 (1)	407
Graphane	13,0	3,488	0,2522 (1)	0,42 (1)	676

It follows from Table 1 that the thickness of the surface layer of all graphene structures does not exceed 10 nm, i.e. they represent a nanostructure, at least in the

z plane (Fig. 12a). Graphite, graphite oxide and fluoro-graphite have 3 graphene monolayers each (Fig. 13), which confirms model (1).

Figure 13. – Change in graphene parameters depending on the number of layers (a) [41, 42]; Raman scattering of graphene oxide depending on the number of layers (b) [12, 13]

The first monolayer of graphite is graphene, it is determined by the unique physicochemical properties of graphene, such as a large theoretical specific surface area (~ 2600 m²/g), charge carrier mobility (~ 200,000 cm²/V•s), high Young's modulus (~ 1000 GPa), thermal conductivity (~ 5000 W/m K), optical transparency (~ 97.7%), mechanical strength, etc. [41, 43].

Bilayer graphene differs from single-layer graphene and graphite. It is studied [44] due to the controlled band gap. An analogue of bilayer graphene is SW graphene, which is more stable than graphene [45]. Three-layer graphene differs from the latter two in mobility and conductivity [46]. A special feature of three-layer graphene is that after its magic-angle torsion it develops superconductivity, which can withstand magnetic fields 2-3 times greater than the Pauli limit for spin-singlet pairing [47]. In [48], superlattices based on

single-layer and double-layer graphene are considered. They are actively studied for use in optoelectronics, acoustics, nanoplasmonics, etc. The author of [48] showed that, based on the analysis of the dispersion equations of a superlattice consisting of alternating strips of single-layer and double-layer graphene, the parameters of the energy spectrum of which can be adjusted by changing the external electric field perpendicular to the surface of the sample, obtained using the Kronig-Penny model, it is shown that the energy spectrum of such a superlattice can be approximated by the Kane model. The absorption coefficient of light during interband transitions in such a structure is calculated.

In [49], a method for producing single-layer graphene oxide films of large area on the surface of semiconductor silicon substrates by deposition from aqueous suspensions was proposed. Graphene oxide was

synthesized from natural crystalline graphite in the process of chemical oxidation and is a wide-bandgap dielectric material.

In [50], the change in the interlayer distance in a thin film consisting of two-layer graphene oxide under the action of water vapor was studied using the AFM

Figure 14. - Spectral position and FWHM of peaks D depending on temperature [12]

Fluorinated graphene can be exfoliated from graphite fluoride in various solvents with/without surfactants using ultrasound [51] or mechanical exfoliation [52]. The resulting material was then exfoliated

into single-layer and bilayer films [53]. Bilayer films play a special role [54] (Fig. 15).

Figure 15. - Bilayer structure formed by fluorinated graphene and polyvinyl alcohol (FG/PVA) layers: (a) schematic representation of the structure; (b) AFM image of the surface of the printed FG/PVA film; (c) TEM image of the partially fluorinated graphene film, arrows indicate the FG matrix and the non-fluorinated region of graphene; (d) SEM images of the printed Ag/FG/PVA structures [54].

In [55], the issue of the influence of concentration (up to 70%) and mutual geometric arrangement of hydrogen atoms on the surface on the electronic properties of partially hydrogenated graphene was considered. The objects under consideration were structures with

periodically arranged hydrogenated regions (Fig. 16). A general effect of changing the electronic properties of graphene with periodically arranged hydrogenated regions was discovered.

Figure 16. - Transition from a pure graphene sheet to a graphane sheet (graphene on the left, fully hydrogenated graphene sheet - graphane on the right); the insets show the band structures of graphene and graphane [55]

In the case of a hexagonal arrangement of hydrogen, the density of the electron wave function is localized directly near the graphane islands, which leads to the formation of a band gap. The complex behavior of the band gap width on the concentration of hydrogen adsorbed on the surface is shown. For structures with

the same concentration value, the band gap width differs by several times, which is evident in the example of nanostructures with a hydrogen concentration of > 40%.

Using (2-6), we determine the elastic properties (Table 2).

Table 2.

Elastic parameters of graphene structures

Carbon	$W_{aa}, J/m^2$	$W_{ac}, J/m^2$	E_{da}, eV	E_{dc}, eV
Graphite	2,853	1,690	2,27 (547 nm)	1,42
Graphene	5,304	-	2,00 (620 nm)	-
Graphite oxide	2, 897	1,757	2,91 (427 nm)	1,82
Graphene oxide	2,588	-	2,59 (477 nm)	-
Fluorographite	0,541	0,180	1,02 (1216 nm)	0,34
Fluorographene	0,610	-	1,15 (1078 nm)	-
Graphane	1,352	-	0,53 (2340 nm)	-

According to the work [56], the deformation energy E_d under external influence is spent on heat, acoustic emission, field emission and luminescence. Let us consider the luminescence of graphene structures. Let us compare the results obtained in Table 2 with the experimental values obtained in various works. Let us

start with the work [57], where the IR laser radiation of carbon materials was studied. Broadband emission spectra were found in the visible region of the spectrum (Fig. 17).

Figure 17. - Emission spectra of carbon materials: polygraphite (1) and technical carbon (2) in vacuum (a) and in air (b) [57]

From Figure 17, one can see a large coincidence of the spectra for graphite. We did not find any literary sources on graphene's luminescence. Let's compare Table 2 with the visible range (Figure 18).

VISIBLE SPECTRUM

Figure 18. – Visible wavelength range

Table 2 and Fig. 18 show that graphene luminescence falls in an inconvenient region on the edge of IR radiation (invisible light), while for graphite it falls in the green region of luminescence. In [58], it was shown that acid-treated graphene samples, as well as reduced graphene oxide, show quite intense blue emission (Fig. 19). Blue emission from graphene oxide-based materials can be combined with yellow emission from materials such as ZnO to produce white light sources..

Figure 19. - Luminescence spectra of graphite oxide (FEG) and graphene oxide (FHG) [58]

From Fig. 19 and Table 2 and Fig. 17, their coincidence in the blue region is visible. In aqueous solutions, the luminescence of graphene oxide flakes is shown in Fig. 20.

Figure 20. – Luminescence spectra of graphene oxide flakes at different excitation energies (a); and at different PH values (b) [59]

From Fig. 20 it is evident that the luminescence spectra of graphene oxide flakes shift to the red region.

From Table 2 it follows that, like graphene, fluorographite, fluorographene and graphane luminesce in the IR region of emission, but not in the visible region.

The adhesion energy of fluorographene is almost 7 times lower than that of graphene (Table 2). Penkov

O.V. [60] examined the tribological properties of graphene and came to the conclusion that the key factors influencing the tribological properties of graphene are the adhesion energy, the number of layers, the laying mode and the substrate material. As for the number of layers, this number is almost the same for graphite and fluorographite, but the adhesion energy differs significantly. This can be seen from Fig. 21..

Figure 21. Schematic and typical result of modeling a deformed configuration for systems: with low adhesion (a); change in the friction force F_f depending on the normal load. The inset shows the change in the lateral force and potential energy as a function of lateral displacement under the action of a normal load of 18.3 nN; with high adhesion (b); change in the friction force F_f depending on the normal load. The inset shows the change in the lateral force and the total potential energy of the system as a function of lateral displacement under a normal load of -61.8 nN (b) [61].

It follows from Fig. 21 that fluorographene is significantly superior to graphene in tribological properties and has potential for use as a friction modifier for plastic lubricants [62].

Conclusion

A comparison of graphene structures (Tables 1 and 2) showed that they all contain three graphene monolayers, each of which differs from each other and from the volume of the crystal, thereby providing wide scope for their practical use. Further research is needed in this direction.

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